

MICROSTRUCTURE AND PROPERTIES OF TiB₂-TiAl COMPOSITES SHEETS PREPARED BY FOIL METALLURGY

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Abstract

Detailed microstructure and mechanical properties of innovative TiB₂-TiAl composite sheet prepared by hot rolling of Ti-(TiB₂/Al) laminates and subsequent reaction annealing has been systemically investigated. The TiB₂-TiAl composite show a typical micro-laminated structure consisting of lamellar TiAl layers and TiB₂-rich layers. Tensile properties testing shows that with increasing temperature from ambient temperature to 700°C, the tensile properties have a sharp increase because of an increase of energy dissipation by plastic deformation and the reduction of the sensitivity to microcrack formation. It is noteworthy that the fracture toughness has significantly improved and the highest value is 15.6 MPa·m^{1/2}, which approaches that of TiAl reinforced with TiNb fiber. Toughening mechanism contains crack deflection caused by TiB₂-rich layers, crack branching and TiB₂-rich/TiAl interface delamination.

1 General Introduction

Gamma-TiAl (γ -TiAl) alloys have great potential for aerospace and automotive applications because of their attracted properties and thus are considered as one of the most promising lightweight high-temperature structural materials [1, 2]. Recently, much attention has been paid to the production of γ -TiAl alloys sheets or foils, which is suitable for thermal protection or exhaust honeycomb structures [3, 4]. However, owing to the limited ductility and poor workability of γ -TiAl, γ -TiAl sheets or foils can be only manufactured above 1100°C with extremely low strain rate [5, 6]; furthermore, relatively expensive equipment and specialized pack materials are required. Therefore, researchers have exploited elemental foil metallurgy technique [1, 7-9]: pure Ti and Al elemental foils with excellent

plastic deformability are stacked to obtain Ti-Al laminates and the laminates are subsequently reaction annealed to produce monolithic γ -TiAl sheets. One of the most significant advantages of this method is to avoid the direct deformation and processing of brittle TiAl-based alloys bullets and can realize the near-net-shape forming of TiAl-based sheets. However, the relative density and mechanical properties of final monolithic TiAl are rather low; in particular, the high temperature strength can not satisfy the requirement for aerospace applications. Therefore, TiB₂/Al composite foils were utilized to replace pure Al foils and Ti-(TiB₂/Al) laminates were manufactured by hot rolling, and subsequent multi-step reaction annealing were employed to produce micro-laminated TiAl matrix composite sheets which can combine respective advantages of intermetallic compounds and ceramic particles. Furthermore, the laminated composites can dramatically improve many properties including the improvement of crack propagation resistance and/or provide enhanced high temperature strength because of the multi-interface effects [10-12]. However, the microstructure of innovative micro-laminated TiAl matrix composite sheets need to further observation and up to now, few investigations focus on the mechanical properties of the innovative micro-laminated TiB₂-TiAl composite sheets. In the present work, the microstructures of TiB₂-TiAl composite sheets with unique micro-laminated structure are investigated in detail and the high-temperature tensile properties and fracture toughness have been studied, with the emphasis on the relationship between mechanical properties and micro-laminated structure.

2 Experimental Procedures

Thin commercial pure Ti foils with thickness of 200 μ m and in-house fabricated 5 vol. % TiB₂/Al (Al

matrix with 99.7% purity) composite sheets with the thickness of 200 μm were cut into 50 mm \times 50 mm squares. Surface pre-treated Ti and TiB_2/Al sheets were alternately stacked to form a “sandwich” and encapsulated in Al alloys packing and then hot-rolled at 510 $^\circ\text{C}$ with a 60% reduction in thickness to produce Ti-(TiB_2/Al) laminates, the microstructure of hot-rolled sample is shown in Fig. 1. The laminates were annealed in a vacuum furnace as follows: i) initial annealing at 1200 $^\circ\text{C}$ for 20min under 0.1 MPa to completely consume Al and obtain TiAl_3 phases and subsequent densification treatment in vacuum ($\sim 10^{-2}$ Pa) under 50 MPa at 1260 $^\circ\text{C}$ for 2h to enclose the Kirkendall voids formed during the initial annealing process; ii) second annealing for composition homogenization at 1250 $^\circ\text{C}$ for 15h; iii) final annealing at 1400 $^\circ\text{C}$ for 15 min in order to obtain TiAl matrix with the lamellar structure consisting of alternating γ -TiAl and α_2 - Ti_3Al . The final thickness of the micro-laminated TiB_2 -TiAl composite sheets is in the range of 3.0–3.2 mm.

Microstructure observation, chemical composition analysis and phase identification of the final micro-laminated TiB_2 -TiAl composite sheets containing different contents of TiB_2 were carried out using scanning electron microscopy (SEM, FEI Quanta 200F) equipped with energy dispersive X-ray spectrometer (EDX) and a transmission electron microscope (TEM, FEI Tecnai F30, 200kv). All SEM images were taken in the back-scattered electrons (BSE) mode. In addition, X-ray diffraction (XRD) was used to identify different phases. All the samples are examined in the rolling direction (RD) – normal direction (ND) plane.

Mechanical properties of the final micro-laminated TiB_2 -TiAl composite sheets were evaluated by tensile testing at ambient and 700 $^\circ\text{C}$ and room temperature fracture toughness testing. The tensile samples were cut parallel to the rolling direction using electrical discharge machining (EDM) and their surfaces were carefully polished to remove the machining traces. The cross-section of tensile samples was 2.5 mm \times 1.5 mm and the gauge length was 15mm. The tensile tests were carried out at room temperature and 700 $^\circ\text{C}$ with an Instron-1186 universal testing machine with the initial strain rate of $1.3 \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$. The samples were mechanically polished using 00-grade silicon carbide papers to remove surface scratches prior to testing.

The fracture toughness measurement was carried out using three-point bend tests on the single edge notched bend (SENB) specimens with the dimensions of 20 mm \times 4 mm \times 2 mm where the

loading span is 16 mm. The straight notch was introduced at the center part of the test bar using a 100 μm wide diamond blade with a notch depth of 0.5 W (the width of the specimen). Two types of fracture toughness specimens with notch orientation parallel to TD and ND were prepared, as shown in Figure 2. Fracture surfaces of tensile specimens and the crack initiation and propagation also examined using a scanning electron microscope.

Fig. 1. Microstructure of the hot-rolled Ti-(TiB_2/Al) laminates (a) the multi-layered structure consisting of alternating Ti layer and TiB_2/Al layer; (b) showing the excellent interfacial bonding and no intermetallic compounds formation at the interface between Ti layer and TiB_2/Al layer

Fig. 2. Two types of fracture toughness specimens with notch orientation in the parallel to (a) transverse direction (TD); (b) normal direction (ND)

3 Results and Discuss

3.1 Microstructure features

The multi-layered Ti-(TiB₂/Al) laminates are subjected to roll bonding and subsequent four-stage annealing between 660 °C and 1400 °C is used to produce the TiAl matrix composite sheets. XRD pattern of the resulting TiAl matrix composite is shown in Fig. 2(a), indicating the presence of the close-packed hexagonal Ti₃Al with DO₁₉ structure and TiB₂ and the tetragonal L1₀ TiAl. This implies TiB₂ particles do not participate in any reaction and are completely retained.

Fig. 3. X-ray diffraction (XRD) pattern of resulting micro-laminated TiB₂-TiAl composite sheets

The detailed microstructure features of the resulting composite sheets are shown in Fig. 4. As shown in Fig. 4, the resulting composite sheet displays a typical multi-layered structure consisting of TiB₂ particles stacking layer (denoted as TiB₂-rich layer) with 5μm wide and TiAl layer with an average width

of 120μm. TEM images shown in Fig. 5(a) including the inset indicate that TiB₂-rich layer is actually composed of numerous TiB₂ particles and a small quantity of TiAl. The interfacial bonding between TiB₂ particles and TiAl is rather compact and no voids are found within TiB₂-rich layers. According to SEM/EDX, the compositions of TiAl layer contain 47.2-53 at. % Ti and the remaining content of Al, which corresponds to lamellar (α₂-Ti₃Al+γ-TiAl) phase. Representative microstructure of lamellar (α₂-Ti₃Al+γ-TiAl) layer is shown in Fig. 5(b). As shown in Fig. 4 and Fig. 5, the size of (α₂+γ) lamellar colony is between 70μm and 150μm with an average value of 100μm and the average spacing of γ-TiAl and α₂-Ti₃Al lamellae is 150 nm, and γ-TiAl and α₂-Ti₃Al follows the orientation relationship: [11-20]α₂//[1-10]γ and (0001)α₂//(111)γ. The lamellar colony size is much smaller than that in the γ-TiAl alloys produced by conventional casting technique (approximately 500 μm–several mm) [13, 14]. This is because the TiB₂-rich layer significantly hinders the growth of the lamellar colony. It is noteworthy that the thickness ratio of TiB₂-rich and TiAl layers can be conveniently adjusted by varying the volume fraction of TiB₂ in TiB₂/Al composite and the respective thickness of TiB₂/Al composite foils and commercial pure Ti foils. Consequently, the microstructures of novel micro-laminated TiB₂-TiAl composite sheets can be devised and controlled by accommodating the thickness of pure Ti foils and TiB₂/Al composite foils and the volume fraction of the reinforcement TiB₂ particles in TiB₂/Al composite foils. Therefore, TiB₂-TiAl composite sheets with novel micro-laminated structure can be successfully fabricated using roll bonding and subsequent reaction annealing of Ti-(TiB₂/Al) laminate.

Fig. 4. (a) representative backscattered electron images of micro-laminated TiB₂TiAl composite sheets; (b) the interface between TiB₂-rich layer and fully lamellar TiAl layer

Fig. 5. (a) TEM images and selected area electron diffraction (SAED) patterns of the TiB_2 -rich layer; (b) microstructure and SAED images of fully lamellar TiAl consisting of α_2 - Ti_3Al and γ -TiAl

3.2 Tensile properties testing

The tensile properties of micro-laminated TiB_2 -TiAl composite sheets tested at ambient temperature and 700 °C are indicated in Fig. 6(a). The ultimate tensile strength (σ_{UTS}), yield strength (σ_y) and total elongation at fracture (δ) of the sheets at ambient temperature are 215.6 MPa, 201.5 MPa and 0.36 %, respectively. The overall fracture surface of the composite at room temperature (Fig. 6(b)) is very flat and has some large cleavage faces, indicating a typical brittle failure. The reason why the micro-laminated composite sheets exhibit low room-temperature tensile properties is that the TiB_2 -rich layers are rather brittle at room temperature. As a result, a fracture process can be rapid and the strength of the multi-layered composite sheets cannot be fully exploited. However, the composite sheets show excellent high-temperature properties. At 700 °C, the σ_{UTS} , σ_y and δ rise to 312.6 MPa, 300.8 MPa and 3.08 %, respectively, higher than those of monolithic TiAl prepared by roll bonding and reaction annealing of Ti-Al laminates [7]. With increasing testing temperature, the total elongation at fracture shows a sharp increase (Fig.

6(a)) owing to the activation of additional slip systems, which approaches the value of monolithic TiAl prepared by roll bonding and reaction underway annealing [7]. Fig. 6(c) shows the fracture surface of the specimen tested at 700 °C, which demonstrates the tearing-out deformation structure within the lamellar colony and the crack propagates by means of interlamellar and/or translamellar, while the fracture surface at ambient temperature is nearly free of deformation structure. The room-temperature toughness of TiAl-based materials is sensitive to microstructure, e.g. pores, and the cleavage fracture occurs generally on low-index crystallographic planes. High temperature tends to decrease the yield points and to enhance plastic deformation. Thus, during crack propagation the energy dissipation by plastic deformation becomes more important, the higher the test temperature [15]. In the micro-laminated TiB_2 -TiAl composite sheets, at a higher temperature dislocations can glide and climb due to thermal activation. Deformation processes can easily spread within the plastic zone of the cracks so that the constraints due to the local slip geometry are less restrictive. Therefore, the fracture mechanism of micro-laminated TiB_2 -TiAl composite sheets

changes from a cleavage-dominated fracture at ambient temperature to an energy-absorbing ductile fracture at high temperature. The detailed

investigation of the dislocation activity during high-temperature deformation is a part of ongoing research.

Fig. 6. (a) tensile properties of the resulting TiB₂-TiAl composite sheets with innovative micro-laminated structure; and the fracture surfaces of samples tested at (b) room temperature with cleavage fracture and (c) 700 °C with the tearing-out feature.

3.3 Fracture toughness testing

Fracture toughness measurement was carried out using three-point bend tests on the single edge

notched bend (SENB) specimens on the Instron-1186 universal testing machine. Fracture toughness was calculated by means of the following equation [16]:

$$K_{Ic} = 3PL\sqrt{10a}/(200bh^2) [1.93 - 3.07(a/h) + 14.53(a/h)^2 - 25.07(a/h)^3 + 25.80(a/h)^4] \quad (1)$$

where K_{Ic} is the fracture toughness ($\text{MPa}\cdot\text{m}^{1/2}$), P is the maximum fracture load (N), L is the span of loading (mm), b is the width of specimen, h is the thickness of specimen, a is the length of the slit notch.

Table 1 compares fracture toughness of micro-laminated TiB₂-TiAl composite sheets with different notch orientations with the values provided in references [17, 18]. It is evident that fracture toughness of micro-laminated TiB₂-TiAl composite sheets with notch orientation parallel to ND is superior to that parallel to TD, which is much higher than that of as-sintered TiAl and 10 vol. %

TiC/TiAl [17] and comparable to the value of TiAl composite reinforced with TiNb fibers. This means micro-laminated TiB₂-TiAl composite sheets exhibit a good characteristic of delayed fracture. As shown in Fig. 7(a) and Fig. 7(b), there is only one main crack nucleating near tip of the initial notch and propagating parallel to the initial notch direction with tortuous or zigzag path. However, for the samples with notch in parallel to TD, only crack deflection can be discovered, while for the samples with notch in parallel to ND, crack deflection occurs along or at close proximity to the TiB₂/TiAl interfaces, crack branching and TiB₂-

rich/TiAl interface delamination has even been observed. Due to the thermal mismatch between TiB₂-rich layer and TiAl layer, the residual stress around TiB₂-rich/TiAl interfaces can not be released by brittle TiAl or TiB₂-rich layers and remains, making the interface delamination easier. Nevertheless, the crack blunting which commonly appears in the laminated systems containing at least one ductile component [19, 20] has not been found. Therefore, the crack deflection caused by TiB₂-rich layers, and crack branching and TiB₂-rich/TiAl

interface delamination, leading to more tortuous crack propagation path which means more energy absorption, are considered as key reasons of superior fracture toughness of micro-laminated TiB₂-TiAl composite sheets with notch orientation parallel to ND. Fracture surfaces of fracture toughness testing are shown in Fig. 7(c) and Fig. 7(d), indicating the failure occurred by a typical cleavage mode and the crack propagate by means of interlamellar and translamellar fracture, regardless of the notch orientation.

Table 1 Comparison of fracture toughness of micro-laminated TiB₂-TiAl composite sheets tested at ambient temperature with the data given in Ref. [16] and [17].

Material systems	As-sintered TiAl [16]	10 vol. % TiC/TiAl[16]	TiNb/TiAl [17]	Micro-laminated TiB ₂ -TiAl composite sheets (Present work)	
				Parallel to transverse direction	Parallel to normal direction
Fracture toughness K_{Ic} (MPa·m ^{1/2})	12.1	13.7	15	11.85±0.64	15.58±0.51

Fig. 7. Crack propagation routes ((a) and (b)) and fracture surfaces ((c) and (d)) of micro-laminated TiB₂-TiAl composite sheets with notch orientation parallel to (a) and (c) transverse direction (TD); (b) and (d) normal direction (ND).

4 Conclusions

Roll bonding and subsequent reaction annealing can be considered as a feasible method for the fabrication of dense TiB₂-TiAl composite sheets with micro-laminated structure. It is noteworthy that the thickness ratio of TiB₂-rich and γ -TiAl/ α_2 -Ti₃Al layers in the composite can be controlled by variation in the initial volume contribution of TiB₂, Al and Ti. The composite is fairly brittle when tested at ambient temperature, while both the strength and elongation is significantly improved when tested at 700 °C. Compared with monolithic TiAl prepared by roll bonding and reaction annealing, tensile strength at 700 °C of the novel TiB₂-TiAl composite sheets is significantly improved due to the introduction of TiB₂-rich layer and the unique micro-laminated microstructure. In addition, the micro-laminated TiB₂-TiAl composite sheets show enhanced fracture toughness with the highest value of 15.6 MPa·m^{1/2} because of crack deflection, crack branching and TiB₂-rich/TiAl interfaces delamination, increasing energy dissipation. The composite therefore has potential for application as a lightweight high-temperature structural material.

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